

The materials to replicate the study:

The Effect of Requests for User Feedback on Quality of Experience (QoE)

Replication scenario:

The subjects use a software product to perform a task. During the task, the feedback tool, integrated with the software, requests feedback several times randomly. At the end of the software usage, users' perceptions of feedback requests and experience of using the product are collected through a post-questionnaire.

Preparing the software:

As the first step, the software product that will be used in the study should be prepared.

- Download the source code of QoE probe (<https://github.com/farnazfotrousi/QoE-Probe-Android>). The QoE probe is the feedback tool responsible for collecting user feedback about a software product.
- Choose the software product that the users are supposed to give feedback about. You need to access to the source code of the software to integrate the QoE probe with.
- Integrate the QoE probe with the software product, using the guideline for integration and experimentation (<https://github.com/farnazfotrousi/QoE-Probe-Android/blob/master/README.md#installation-and-integration-instructions>).

Note: with the above setting, the user logs are stored in BTH server. If you intend to collect logs on your machine, you need to prepare a servlet to manage the logs. Then change the “webservice_url” in the system.properties located in “/assets” folder to the new address of your servlet.

Preparing the task description:

A task description should be prepared in two sections including the general and task-specific descriptions.

- General descriptions
 - o Identify the goal of the study. (e.g., The goal of the study is to evaluate hands-on

requirements engineering practice by translating a real-world requirements walkthrough into a requirements model.)

- **Specify the role of participants in the task** (e.g., You are a requirements engineer tasked with analysis of the Drug Supply Manager (DSM) solution. The solution's vision statement in the PDF are attached below.)
 - **Provide a general overview of the task** (e.g., You take over the work of a colleague who has run a requirements workshop already, but has left the project. You study the workshop video and analyze the discussed requirements by modelling them.)
 - **Determine the flexibilities of performing the task** (e.g., You are free to decide what kind of modelling you do and what modelling notation you use. Compliance with a known modelling notation does help but is not required. It is important that your models will be understood.)
 - **Identify and share the related materials** (e.g., In the video [here], you will see the following real stakeholders discussing the real DSM system. X: the requirement engineer (striped shirt), ... or also Flexisketch is developed and ...)
 - **Mention that the task should be performed Individually** (e.g., no group work)
 - **Identify conditions to opt out from the study** (e.g., You can opt out from this assignment at any moment and do one of the assignments from the previous years. Write a message to example@bth.se. In this case, we immediately delete all log data.)
- **Task descriptions: Explain the steps of the tasks that the subject should perform. In the following, you can see an example of such description.**
- (e.g.,
1. Get access to an Android device
 - a. Recommended: Android tablet (preferred) or Android smart phone
 - b. Alternatively, you can use one of our laboratory's Android tablets
 2. Prepare yourself as follows:
 - a. Install and run the QoE Probe (allow installation from "unknown source" - no virus contained in APK and source code may be inspected). Ensure that the settings of the probe are like: collect data ON, 1% likelihood, 1 day data submission interval (not 15 days).
 - b. Install and run the Flexisketch modelling tool (allow installation from "unknown source" - no virus contained in APK and source code may be

inspected).

3. Analyze the DSM requirements by modelling the DSM solution according to how the stakeholders define the requirements in the workshop video.
 - a. You have to model the requirements defined from just 15 consecutive minutes from the video. Choose any starting point as long as it is not later than 15 minutes before the video end. Note the chosen starting point.
 - b. Note the starting point in the video (minutes after video start) as well as when you start the modelling with Flexisketch (date and time).
 - c. Document the DSM system with drawings you create with Flexisketch. Ensure that the drawings specify what the stakeholders defined during the 15 minutes of video that you have chosen.
 4. Save your Flexisketch diagrams.
 - a. Save your model in Flexisketch: Select “Export as Image” in the Flexisketch Setting Menu and write the “image_name” in the pop-up dialog. Your model will be saved in the “FlexiSketch” folder in the internal storage. You can access it there with an Android tool like "File Commander".
 5. Create a short Requirements Document with the diagrams you created. No fully fledged IEEE 830-based Specification is needed. Just make a lightweight document perhaps including introduction, specification, and conclusion sections.
 6. Fill in the Questionnaire that you find it attached below. Please be honest (no grades are given for this assignment).
 7. Submit Requirement Report (see task 5) and Questionnaire (see task 6).
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Analyzing the collected data:

Three types of data should be analyzed to answer the research questions: the user feedback about the software product during usage collected from the usage log file, as well as the user feedback that was provided in the post-questionnaire about the feedback requests and the software product.

Contact information

If you have questions or need help, please do not hesitate to contact me: Farnaz Fotrousi (farnaz.fotrousi@ bth.se)